

Climate suitability report of *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola*

[Content of the *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* Zenodo repository](#)

[Xanthomonas_citri_pv.viticola _ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf](#)

The file contains the methodology and results of the Climate Suitability Analysis for *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *Viticola*, describing both the extensive literature search and the climate classification. The results of the databases interrogations are presented together with the process applied for documents screening and selection, summarised by a PRISMA diagram. Four maps illustrate the results of the climate suitability analysis. Although, we refer to the related PRA (EFSA Panel on Plant Health (PLH) et al., 2022). For an exhaustive and more comprehensive discussion of the results of the climate suitability analysis.

[Xanthomonas_citri_pv.viticola _ANNEX_A_Master_file.xlsx](#)

The file contains the list of documents selected for data extraction. The description of the fields is in Xanthomonas_citri_pv.viticola _ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf.

[Xanthomonas_citri_pv.viticola _ANNEX_B_Observations.csv](#)

The file contains the list of the organism observed distribution at a global level. Both punctual locations and administrative units are included.

[Maps in .jpeg format](#)

Maps of Climate Classification Analysis:

- [Global_Xanthomonas_citri_pv.viticola_KG.jpg](#)
- [Europe_Xanthomonas_citri_pv.viticola_KG.jpg](#)
- [India_Xanthomonas_citri_pv.viticola_KG.jpg](#)
- [South_America_Xanthomonas_citri_pv.viticola_KG.jpg](#)

[Xanthomonas_citri_pv.viticola _PRA.gpkg](#)

This is a GeoPackage (.gpkg) file containing the GIS layers of the results of the analysis.

[Xanthomonas_citri_pv.viticola _qgis_styles.zip](#)

The folder contains the QGIS styles to replicate the symbology used in the maps published in the PRA. These styles were applied to the layers contained in Xanthomonas_citri_pv.viticola _PRA.gpkg.

Introduction

Climate suitability analysis allows risk assessors to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest (ISPM 11, 2013). This analysis is typically based on pest biology and/or distribution according to the different methodology/models available (Devorshak, 2012). Because of this, an extensive literature research, in accordance with EFSA systematic review methodology (EFSA, 2010), was performed to gather relevant information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola*. Then, the data extracted from the literature search were used to analyse the climate suitability of *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* in the EU.

Note on this report

This document includes a description of the climate suitability analysis methodology applied to *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola*. The analysis was conducted in the context of the *EFSA Pest risk assessment of Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* for the European Union (EFSA Panel on Plant Health (PLH) et al., 2022). For a complete description and discussion of the results of the present analysis, inserted in the framework of a pest risk assessment, please refer to the related PRA cited above.

Methods

Hereby follows the description of the methodologies adopted to search in scientific databases and analyse the results of the searches. The first section will focus on the systematic literature review, while the second will concern the analysis of the data retrieved from the review.

Systematic literature review

Searches were performed to identify relevant information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola*. Table 1 shows the list of databases that were consulted. Results from the scientific databases were crosschecked and integrated (if needed) with records of the EPPO and CABI databases.

Table 1: List of databases consulted for the extensive literature search

Databases	Platforms
Web of Science Core Collection	Web of Science
Biosis	
CAB Abstracts	
Chinese Science Citation Database	
Current Content Connect	
FSTA- the food science resource	
Korean Journal Database	
Medline	
Russian Science Citation Index	
SciELO Citation Index	
Scopus	Scopus

A combination of the scientific and international common names of the pest, retrieved from CAB Thesaurus¹ and EPPO Global database² (shown in Table 2), was used to interrogate the bibliographic databases. No other keywords were used (e.g., “biology”, “physiology”, “temperature”, etc...) to not

¹ <https://www.cabi.org/publishing-products/cab-thesaurus/>

² <https://gd.eppo.int/>

limit the retrieval of documents that could include information useful for the purposes of this search as secondary information, especially in the case of pest distribution.

Table 2: Scientific and common names found in the consulted databases

Source	Scientific names
EPPO	<i>Xanthomonas citri</i> pv. <i>viticola</i>
EPPO, CAB Thesaurus	<i>Pseudomonas viticola</i>
EPPO, CAB Thesaurus	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>viticola</i>
CAB Thesaurus	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> subsp. <i>viticola</i>
CAB Thesaurus	<i>Xanthomonas campestris viticola</i>
CAB Thesaurus	<i>Xanthomonas viticola</i>
	Common names/disease names
CAB Thesaurus	canker of grapevine
CAB Thesaurus	grapevine leaf spot
EPPO	leaf spot of grapevine

Table 3 shows the query syntax used in Web of Science and Scopus platforms, the date of the search, and the number of documents obtained.

Table 3: Research strings used for the bibliographic databases consulted

Platform	Set	Date of search	Query	Results
Web of Science	#1	15/11/2021	TS=(((("Xanthomonas campestris" OR "x campestris" OR "x. campestris" OR "Xanthomonas citri" OR "X citri" OR "x. citri" OR "Xanthomonas c" OR "Xanthomonas c.") AND (Viticola OR Grapevine OR Grapevines OR "Vitis vinifera"))) OR ((Pseudomonas OR Xanthomonas) NEAR/3 (viticola OR Grapevine OR Grapevines OR "Vitis vinifera")) All Databases excluding Data citation Index and Zoological Report	185
SCOPUS	#1	15/11/2021	TITLE-ABS-KEY(((("Xanthomonas campestris" OR "x campestris" OR "x. campestris" OR "Xanthomonas citri" OR "X citri" OR "x. citri" OR "Xanthomonas c" OR "Xanthomonas c.") AND (Viticola OR Grapevine OR Grapevines OR "Vitis vinifera"))) OR ((Pseudomonas OR Xanthomonas) W/3 (viticola OR Grapevine OR Grapevines OR "Vitis vinifera"))	53

All the references were exported to the reference manager software EndoNoteX9 (The EndNote Team, 2013) and checked for duplicates. References were then imported (as a compressed Endnote library) in the software DistillerSR (Evidence Partners, 2021) and screened.

Document screening

Document screening followed a two-step approach. In both steps the documents were screened answering the question “*Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?*”.

The first step was based on titles and abstracts. It was applied to identify the presence of elements indicating the potential availability of information on physiology, ecology, and distribution of the pest in the full text. In case of positive answer, the type of information potentially available was specified

(i.e. Physiology/Ecology, Distribution, or Other) (see Figure 1:Title and Abstract Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR. Version 2.35. Evidence Partners; 2021. Accessed August-September 2021. <https://www.evidencepartners.com>.)Figure 1 as an example).

Reference Details

RefID: 26, Effect of treatment of 'red globe' vine cuttings on the control of bacterial canker caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *viticola*
 Naué, C. R., Barbosa, M. A. G., Batista, D. C., De Souza, E. B., Mariano, R. L. R.

Attachments

Reference Labels:
 Scopus

The spread of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *viticola* (Xcv), causal agent of grapevine bacterial canker, occurs among other ways, through infected plants and grapevine cuttings. It was studied how to obtain propagation material free of Xcv testing the effectiveness of treatments of cuttings using thermotherapy, bactericides and sanitizers. The Xcv isolates were tested for pathogenicity and in vitro sensitivity to bactericides and sanitizers at different concentrations. The eradication of Xcv on cuttings was tested in experiments with thermotherapy (50°C for 30 and 40 min; 53°C for 5 and 10 min); bactericides [oxytetracycline+copper sulphate (150+2000, 165+2200, 180+2400 and 195+2600 mg L⁻¹ of H₂O) and oxytetracycline (600, 700, 800 and 900 mg L⁻¹)] and sanitizers [dodecylidimethyl ammonium chloride (600, 1200, 1800, 2400 and 3000 µl L⁻¹) sodium hypochlorite (5000, 10000, 20000, 30000 and 40000 µl L⁻¹) and benzalkonium chloride (125, 167, 250, 334 and 500 µl L⁻¹)]. We evaluated the incubation period, the incidence and severity of disease. The bactericidal oxytetracycline and sanitizers dodecylidimethyl ammonium chloride and sodium hypochlorite provided the largest zones of inhibition, in vitro. However, despite the several treatments tested we cannot recommend an efficient condition of temperature/time, and concentrations of bactericides and sanitizers capable of eradicating Xcv from infected grapevine cuttings, thus confirming their great importance for the spread of grapevine bacterial canker. © 2014, Sociedade Brasileira de Fruticultura. All rights reserved.

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1. Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?
 Yes No Unclear

2. Specify what type of information
 Physiology/Ecology Distribution Others

Figure 1:Title and Abstract Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR. Version 2.35. Evidence Partners; 2021. Accessed August-September 2021. <https://www.evidencepartners.com>.)

Selecting the answer “yes” meant that the reference was automatically moved to the next level of screening (i.e. full text screening). When it was unclear whether information of interest was available from the title and the abstract the answer “unclear” was selected, automatically carrying the paper on to the next step. The second step of the screening (Figure 2) was based on the full text of the documents previously selected.

Reference Details

RefID: 26, Effect of treatment of 'red globe' vine cuttings on the control of bacterial canker caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *viticola*
 Naué, C. R., Barbosa, M. A. G., Batista, D. C., De Souza, E. B., Mariano, R. L. R.

Attachments

PDF - 26-2014-Naué.pdf (Standard Version) | (Annotatable Version)

Reference Labels:
 Scopus

The spread of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *viticola* (Xcv), causal agent of grapevine bacterial canker, occurs among other ways, through infected plants and grapevine cuttings. It was studied how to obtain propagation material free of Xcv testing the effectiveness of treatments of cuttings using thermotherapy, bactericides and sanitizers. The Xcv isolates were tested for pathogenicity and in vitro sensitivity to bactericides and sanitizers at different concentrations. The eradication of Xcv on cuttings was tested in experiments with thermotherapy (50°C for 30 and 40 min; 53°C for 5 and 10 min); bactericides [oxytetracycline+copper sulphate (150+2000, 165+2200, 180+2400 and 195+2600 mg L⁻¹ of H₂O) and oxytetracycline (600, 700, 800 and 900 mg L⁻¹)] and sanitizers [dodecylidimethyl ammonium chloride (600, 1200, 1800, 2400 and 3000 µl L⁻¹) sodium hypochlorite (5000, 10000, 20000, 30000 and 40000 µl L⁻¹) and benzalkonium chloride (125, 167, 250, 334 and 500 µl L⁻¹)]. We evaluated the incubation period, the incidence and severity of disease. The bactericidal oxytetracycline and sanitizers dodecylidimethyl ammonium chloride and sodium hypochlorite provided the largest zones of inhibition, in vitro. However, despite the several treatments tested we cannot recommend an efficient condition of temperature/time, and concentrations of bactericides and sanitizers capable of eradicating Xcv from infected grapevine cuttings, thus confirming their great importance for the spread of grapevine bacterial canker. © 2014, Sociedade Brasileira de Fruticultura. All rights reserved.

Submit Form and go to This Form - Next Reference or Skip to Next

1. INHERITED FROM TIAB SCREENING
 Selection criteria in tab
 Physiology/Ecology Distribution Others

2. Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?
 Yes No Unclear (to be consulted)

3. What type of information
 Physiology/Ecology Distribution Other

Figure 2: Full-text Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR. Version 2.35. Evidence Partners; 2021. Accessed August-September 2021. <https://www.evidencepartners.com>.)

Data extraction

Data extraction was performed on two files for the documents passing the full-text screening. One Excel sheet describing all the relevant information extracted, hereafter referred to as master file (ANNEX A), and one other csv file used to record data on pest distribution (ANNEX B).

Table 4: Information extracted from the documents and collected in the master file

Field name	Description	Type
Refid	Record ID. The Refid number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller	Integer
Reference	Full reference for the record	String
Primary_source	Source of info	String
Physiology_Ecology	Presence of information on physiology and/or ecology (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Distribution	Presence of information on distribution (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Other	Presence of additional information that could be of interest. Empty means no information	Boolean
T	Presence of information on temperature (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
RH	Presence of information on relative humidity or moisture (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Photoperiod	Presence of information on photoperiod (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean

Table 4 shows the information extracted from the documents and collected in the master file, while the distribution file (Table 5) contains data on the geographical observations of the pest. To further detail the analysis, an effort was made to categorize, when possible, the observations based on the organism status. Hence, two classifications for the pest status were created. The first one (Species_status1) based on the reported harmfulness of the organism (i.e., Pest, Non-Pest, Unclear), the second (Species_status2) based on the reported persistence of the organism in the observed location (i.e., Persistent, Migrant, or Unclear). An additional table associated to the distribution table and including additional notes and information on specific records was also created as a supporting information.

Table 5: *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* observations extracted from the documents and collected in the distribution file.

Field name	Description	Type
Obs_ID	The Obs_ID is a unique number associated to each collected observation	Integer
Continent	Continent where the organism observation was reported	String
Country	Country where the organism observation was reported	String
State	State where the organism observation was reported	String
Observation	Location of the organism observation as reported in literature	String
Admin.level	FAO GAUL Administrative level of the observation ('location' in the case of specific geographic point)	Integer
Admin.source	Administrative shapefile layer used to identify the area of the organism observation (usually FAO GAUL layer)	String
Admin.code	FAO GAUL Administrative code of the observation ('NA' in the case of specific geographic point)	Integer
Lat	Latitude of the organism observation	Double
Long	Longitude of the organism observation	Double
Google_Earth_coord	Indicates if a centroid was used to identify the organism location. Centroids were used only if the observation was not available in the FAO GAUL Administrative subdivision and in case of relatively small entities like towns/cities/provinces. Empty means that the coordinates were already indicated in the literature or that the location is identified by an administrative layer	Boolean
RefID	Record ID. The Refid number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller. This is the same field used also in Table 4.	Integer
Species_status1	Classifies the organism harmfulness in the area of observation (i.e. Pest, Non-Pest, Unclear)	String
Species_status2	Classifies the organism persistence in the area of observation (i.e. Persistent, Migrant, or Unclear)	String
Notes	Flagged records (with 'x') include additional information saved in the support table	Boolean
Uncertain	Flagged records (with 'x') refer to documents including uncertain information regarding the organism observation (e.g. records from museums, interceptions, not clear information)	Boolean

Climate Classification analysis

The SCAN-Clim tool (EFSA, Maiorano, A., 2022) was used to output climate suitability maps based on the climate classification approach (EFSA and Maiorano, 2022). The approach is based on a Köppen–Geiger climate classification for the period 1986–2010 and on a 10-km grid from the Institute for Veterinary Public Health of the University of Vienna, after Kottek et al. (2006) rescaled after Rubel et al. (2017) (<http://koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at/present.htm>).

The climate types present in the observed locations of *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* were identified and mapped. Since the area of the assessment is the EU, the output maps considered only climate types that are present in this area. Administrative units where the pest was observed are highlighted with black borders, while punctual observations are indicated with red dots.

Results

Systematic literature review

The process followed to identify, screen, and include eligible information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* is summarized in the PRISMA diagram (Moher et al., 2009) in Figure 3. A total of 283 documents were retrieved from the search in scientific databases. Overall, 185 documents were found through the Web of Science platform and 53 through the SCOPUS platform. Six additional references including information on physiology and distribution, found while gathering generic information on the pest in the very first stages of the study, were also added. After excluding duplicates, 215 documents were assessed for the first level screening (title and abstract). Sixty-eight documents were selected for the second level screening (full text). A total of 40

papers were used for the data extraction from scientific databases. Two additional documents, found by the working group experts', were added to this list. Out of these 42 papers, 35 included information on *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* distribution and 21 information on its ecophysiology.

The search on scientific databases was completed on 22nd December 2021.

Figure 3: PRISMA Diagram describing the process followed to identify, screen, and include eligible information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola*.

Observed distribution data

Sixty-seven records of the presence of *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* were collected. The records are all available in the observation file (ANNEX B), including the uncertainty points excluded from the final maps. Out of these records (Figure 4), 43 are punctual observation reporting specific coordinates, or small administrative units (e.g., US counties) for which coordinates from Google Earth were used. Nineteen records are related to larger administrative units, like regions. Five records were excluded

from the final maps due to uncertainties, i.e.: too broad or imprecise observations (reports at Countries and Continents level, unclear finding locations).

The conclusion of the pest categorisation (EFSA, 2021) expressed strong uncertainty on the pest distribution in Thailand. Until the present day, no data on the possible presence of *Xanthomonas citri* pv.*viticola* in Thailand has been published in peer-reviewed journals. The only document found reporting the presence of the pest in the country is a MSc thesis (Buensanteai, 2004), for which detection and identification of the pest were done with ELISA and never confirmed by PCR. Therefore, these observations were mapped but not considered in this analysis.

Climate classification

Figure 5 shows the world distribution of Köppen–Geiger climate types where *Xanthomonas citri* pv.*viticola* was observed. Figure 6 reports the EU territory while Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the same information, focusing on the current pest distribution areas, Southeast Asia and South America respectively. The collected pest distribution points occur partially under temperate-mesothermal climates (indicated by the letter C in the Köppen-Geiger classification), like the Mediterranean hot summer climates (Csa), the oceanic climate (Cfb), and the humid subtropical climate (Cfa). Although, collected data mostly occur under the hot semi-arid climate (BSh).

Observed distribution of *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* in India and South America

- Punctual observation
- Observed Administrative Units

Figure 4: Observed distribution of *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola*. Maps on the left (A1, B1) show punctual locations (with coordinates) where the pest was reported. Maps on the right (A2, B2) show the distribution at the administrative unit level for those areas where punctual observations were not found.

Figure 5: Global map of *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* climate suitability analysis based on the Köppen–Geiger climate classification. Black borders indicate countries/regions where the pest was observed. Red dots indicate punctual observations of the pest (coordinates). Climates not present in EU are not mapped. Legend shows the lists of Köppen-Geiger climate type.

Figure 6: Climate suitability map of *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* for the EU territory, based on the Köppen–Geiger climate classification. Climates not present in EU are not mapped. Legend shows the lists of Köppen-Geiger climates.

Figure 7: Climate suitability map of *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* for Southeast Asia, based on the Köppen–Geiger climate classification. Black borders indicate countries/regions where the pest was reported. Red dots indicate punctual observations of the pest (coordinates). Climates not present in EU are not mapped. Legend shows the lists of Köppen-Geiger climates.

Figure 8: Climate suitability analysis map of *Xanthomonas citri* pv. *viticola* for South America, based on the Köppen–Geiger climate classification. Black borders indicate countries/regions where the pest was observed. Red dots indicate punctual observations of the pest (coordinates). Climates not present in EU are not mapped. Legend shows the lists of Köppen-Geiger climates.

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